

m-IDEALS AND ITS GENERATORS OF TERNARY SEMIGROUPS

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ABSTRACT. The purpose of this paper is to introduce some new classes of *m*-bi ideals and *m*-quasi ideals in ternary semigroups and give some characterizations in terms of bi ideals and quasi ideals. Let U_1 be the *m*-bi ideal of \mathbb{T} and U_2 be the *m*-bi ideal of U_1 such that $U_2^3 = U_2$, shown that U_2 is a *m*-bi ideal of \mathbb{T} . Let U_1, U_2 and U_3 be the three ternary subsemigroups of \mathbb{T} , it has been shown that $U_1U_2U_3$ is a *t*-bi ideal if at least one of U_1, U_2, U_3 is *l*-RI or *m*-LATI or *n*-LI of \mathbb{T} . Also we discuss *m*-bi ideal generated by \mathcal{B} is $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m = \mathcal{B} \cup \sum_{finite} \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}$. Examples are needed strengthen our results.

1. INTRODUCTION

The notion of ternary semigroup is a natural generalization of ternary group. The notion of ideal play very important role to study the algebraic structures. Lehmer initiated the concept of ternary algebraic systems called triplexes in 1932 [7]. A ternary semigroup is a nonempty set together with a ternary multiplication which is associative. The notion of ternary semigroups was known to Banach who is credited with an example of a ternary semigroup which does not reduce to a semigroup. Ternary multiplication compatible with a vector space structure has been studied using both algebraic and functional analytical methods. In [8], Los studied some properties of ternary semigroup and proved that every ternary semigroup can be embedded in a semigroup. In [16], Sioson studied ideal theory in ternary semigroups. The notion of quasi-ideal in semigroup and in ring has been introduced by Steinfeld. In ternary semigroups, quasi-ideals are generalization of right ideals, lateral ideals and left ideals whereas bi-ideals are generalization of quasi-ideals. It is interesting to note that many of the results of semigroup theory can be obtained for ternary semigroups using various ideal concepts. If A, B and C are three subsets of ternary semigroups, $ABC = \left\{ \sum_{finite} a_i b_i c_i : a_i \in A, b_i \in B, c_i \in C \right\}$. Our aim in this paper is threefold.

- (1) To study the relationship between bi ideal and *m*-bi ideal.
- (2) To study the relationship between *m*-quasi ideal and *m*-bi ideal.
- (3) To characterize generators of bi ideal, left ideal and right ideal.

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2. PRELIMINARIES

From now onward, unless stated otherwise, \mathbb{T} will denote a ternary semigroups.

Definition 2.1. [15] A ternary semigroup is a nonempty set \mathbb{T} together with a ternary operation $(a, b, c) \rightarrow [abc]$ satisfying the associative law $[[abc]uv] = [a[bcu]v] = [ab[cuv]]$, $\forall a, b, c, u, v \in \mathbb{T}$.

Definition 2.2. [15] A non empty subset A of \mathbb{T} is said to be

- (i) ternary subsemigroup (shortly TSS) if $A^3 = AAA \subseteq A$.
- (ii) left ideal (shortly LI) if $\mathbb{T}TA \subseteq A$.
- (iii) right ideal (shortly RI) if $ATT \subseteq A$.
- (iv) lateral ideal (shortly LAT) if $TAT \subseteq A$.
- (v) an ideal if it is a left, right and lateral ideal.

Definition 2.3. [15] For any non empty subset A of \mathbb{T}

- (i) $A_l = A \cup \mathbb{T}TA$ is the left ideal generated by A .
- (ii) $A_r = A \cup ATT$ is the right ideal generated by A .
- (iii) $A_{lat} = A \cup TAT \cup TTATT$ is the lateral ideal generated by A .
- (iv) $(A) = A \cup \mathbb{T}TA \cup ATT \cup TAT \cup TTATT$ is the ideal generated by A .

Definition 2.4. (i) A TSS B of \mathbb{T} is called a bi-ideal if $BTB \subseteq B$.
 (ii) A TSS Q of \mathbb{T} is called a quasi-ideal if $Q\mathbb{T} \cap (\mathbb{T}Q \cup \mathbb{T}TQ\mathbb{T}) \cap \mathbb{T}TQ \subseteq Q$.

Definition 2.5. (i) A subsemigroup L of semigroup S is called an l -left ideal if $S^l L \subseteq L$.
 (ii) A subsemigroup N of semigroup S is called an n -right ideal if $NS^n \subseteq N$, where l, n are positive integers.

Remark. For a semigroup S and l, m are positive integers, $S^m = S \cdot S \cdot S \cdot \dots \cdot S$ (m - times). Now $S^2 = S \cdot S \subseteq S$ and $S^3 = S \cdot S \cdot S \subseteq S^2 \subseteq S$. We conclude that $S^l \subseteq S^m$ such that $l \geq m$. Consequently $S^m \subseteq S$.

3. VARIOUS m -IDEALS

Here m -bi ideals (shortly $m\mathcal{B}$) and m -quasi ideals (shortly mQ) are introduced.

Definition 3.1. The $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} is a TSS of \mathbb{T} such that $\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$, where $m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Remark. If $m = 1$, then 1-bi ideal is simply bi ideal of \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 3.1. For $m \geq 1$, Every bi ideal is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Proof. Let \mathcal{B} be the bi ideal of \mathbb{T} , then $\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$. Now, $\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^1\mathcal{B} = \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$. Also, $\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^2\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^1\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$. Continuing like these, $\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^{m-1}\mathcal{B} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$. Therefore \mathcal{B} is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Converse of the Theorem 3.1 is not true which can be illustrated as follows.

Example 3.2. Consider the ternary semigroups

$$\mathbb{T} = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccccc} 0 & x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & x_4 & x_5 \\ 0 & 0 & x_6 & x_7 & x_8 & x_9 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x_{10} & x_{11} & x_{12} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & x_{13} & x_{14} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & x_{15} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right) \mid x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_0^-, i = 1, 2, \dots, 15 \right\}.$$

Clearly $\mathcal{B} = \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{cccccc} 0 & x & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right) \mid x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}_0^- \right\}$ is a TSS.

Hence \mathcal{B} is a 2-bi ideal but not bi ideal of \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 3.2. *The product of any three $m\mathcal{B}^s$ with identity element e is a $m\mathcal{B}^s$ of \mathbb{T} .*

Proof. Let Z_1, Z_2 and Z_3 be the three $m\mathcal{B}^s$ of \mathbb{T} with bipotencies m_1, m_2 and m_3 respectively. Then $Z_1\mathbb{T}^{m_1}Z_1\mathbb{T}^{m_1}Z_1 \subseteq Z_1$, $Z_2\mathbb{T}^{m_2}Z_2\mathbb{T}^{m_2}Z_2 \subseteq Z_2$ and $Z_3\mathbb{T}^{m_3}Z_3\mathbb{T}^{m_3}Z_3 \subseteq Z_3$, where $m_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$. Put $t = \max m_i$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$

$$\begin{aligned} (Z_1Z_2Z_3)^3 &= (Z_1Z_2Z_3)(Z_1Z_2Z_3)(Z_1Z_2Z_3) \\ &\subseteq (Z_1(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}Z_1)(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}Z_1))Z_2Z_3 \\ &= (Z_1(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}eee\dots eZ_1)(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}eee\dots eZ_1))Z_2Z_3 \\ &\subseteq (Z_1(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\dots\mathbb{T}Z_1)(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\dots\mathbb{T}Z_1))Z_2Z_3 \\ &= (Z_1\mathbb{T}^mZ_1\mathbb{T}^mZ_1)Z_2Z_3 \\ &\subseteq Z_1Z_2Z_3. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (Z_1Z_2Z_3)\mathbb{T}^t(Z_1Z_2Z_3)\mathbb{T}^t(Z_1Z_2Z_3) &= Z_1(Z_2Z_3\mathbb{T}^t)Z_1(Z_2Z_3\mathbb{T}^t)(Z_1Z_2Z_3) \\ &\subseteq Z_1(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^t)Z_1(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^t)(Z_1Z_2Z_3) \\ &= Z_1\mathbb{T}^{2+t}Z_1\mathbb{T}^{2+t}(Z_1Z_2Z_3) \\ &\subseteq (Z_1\mathbb{T}^{m_1}Z_1\mathbb{T}^{m_1})Z_1Z_2Z_3 \\ &= (Z_1\mathbb{T}^{m_1}Z_1\mathbb{T}^{m_1}Z_1)Z_2Z_3 \\ &\subseteq Z_1Z_2Z_3 \end{aligned}$$

Thus $Z_1Z_2Z_3$ is an m -bi ideal of \mathbb{T} with bipotency $\max m_i$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Theorem 3.3. *If Z is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} and T_1, T_2 are two TSS^s with e , then ZT_1T_2, T_1ZT_2 and T_1T_2Z are $m\mathcal{B}^s$ of \mathbb{T} .*

Proof. Let Z be $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} and T_1, T_2 are two TSS^s with e .

$$\begin{aligned} (ZT_1T_2)^3 &= (ZT_1T_2)(ZT_1T_2)(ZT_1T_2) \\ &\subseteq (Z(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}Z)(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}Z))T_1T_2 \\ &= (Z(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}eee\dots eZ)(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}eee\dots eZ))T_1T_2 \\ &\subseteq (Z(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\dots\mathbb{T}Z)(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\dots\mathbb{T}Z))T_1T_2 \\ &= (Z\mathbb{T}^mZ\mathbb{T}^mZ)T_1T_2 \\ &\subseteq ZT_1T_2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (ZT_1T_2)\mathbb{T}^m(ZT_1T_2)\mathbb{T}^m(ZT_1T_2) &= Z(T_1T_2\mathbb{T}^m)Z(T_1T_2\mathbb{T}^m)(ZT_1T_2) \\ &\subseteq Z(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^m)Z(\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^m)(ZT_1T_2) \\ &= Z\mathbb{T}^{2+m}Z\mathbb{T}^{2+m}(ZT_1T_2) \\ &\subseteq (Z\mathbb{T}^mZ\mathbb{T}^m)ZT_1T_2 \\ &= (Z\mathbb{T}^mZ\mathbb{T}^mZ)T_1T_2 \\ &\subseteq ZT_1T_2. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, ZT_1T_2 is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Similarly T_1ZT_2 and T_1T_2Z are $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 3.4. *If Z is a $m\mathcal{B}$ and T_1 is a TSS of \mathbb{T} , then $Z \cap T_1$ is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of T_1 .*

Proof. Since $Z \cap T_1 \subseteq Z$ and $Z \cap T_1 \subseteq T_1$, $(Z \cap T_1)(Z \cap T_1)(Z \cap T_1) \subseteq ZZZ \subseteq Z$.
 $(Z \cap T_1)T_1^m(Z \cap T_1)T_1^m(Z \cap T_1) \subseteq (Z \cap T_1)T_1^m(Z \cap T_1)T_1^m(Z \cap T_1) \subseteq ZT_1^mZT_1^m \subseteq Z$.
 Therefore $Z \cap T_1$ is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of T_1 .

Theorem 3.5. *The intersection of family of $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} is a $m\mathcal{B}$ with potencies m_i and potency $\max m_i$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$.*

Remark. *Sum of two $m\mathcal{B}$ s of \mathbb{T} is not a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .*

Example 3.3. Consider the ternary semigroup $\mathbb{T} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & a_3 \\ a_4 & a_5 & a_6 \\ a_7 & a_8 & a_9 \end{pmatrix} \mid a_i \in \mathbb{Z}_0^- \right\}$.

Let $X_1 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid p \in \mathbb{Z}_0^- \right\}$ and $X_2 = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & q \end{pmatrix} \mid q \in \mathbb{Z}_0^- \right\}$ are $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} but $X_1 + X_2$ is not a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Definition 3.4. A TSS Q of \mathbb{T} is called a mQ if $Q\mathbb{T}^m \cap \mathbb{T}^m Q\mathbb{T}^m \cap \mathbb{T}^m Q \subseteq Q$.

Remark. *If $m = 1$, then 1-quasi ideal is simply quasi ideal of \mathbb{T} .*

Theorem 3.6. *Every mQ is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .*

Proof. Let N be mQ of \mathbb{T} . Now,

$$\begin{aligned} N\mathbb{T}^m N\mathbb{T}^m N &\subseteq N\mathbb{T}^m \mathbb{T}^m \mathbb{T}^m \\ &= N\mathbb{T}^{m+1} \mathbb{T}^{m+1} \\ &\subseteq N\mathbb{T}^m \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $N\mathbb{T}^m N\mathbb{T}^m N \subseteq \mathbb{T}^m N\mathbb{T}^m$ and $N\mathbb{T}^m N\mathbb{T}^m N \subseteq \mathbb{T}^m N$.

Thus, $N\mathbb{T}^m N\mathbb{T}^m N \subseteq (N\mathbb{T}^m) \cap (\mathbb{T}^m N\mathbb{T}^m) \cap (\mathbb{T}^m N) \subseteq N$.

Converse of the above Theorem is not true by the following Example.

Example 3.5. Consider the ternary semigroup

$$\mathbb{T} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & x_4 & x_5 \\ 0 & 0 & x_6 & x_7 & x_8 & x_9 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & x_{10} & x_{11} & x_{12} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & x_{13} & x_{14} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & x_{15} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid x_i \in \mathbb{Z}_0^-, i = 1, 2, \dots, 15 \right\}.$$

Clearly $Q = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & x & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & y & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \mid x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}_0^- \right\}$ is a TSS.

Hence Q is a 2-bi ideal but not 2-quasi ideal of \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 3.7. *Product of three $(l, m, n)Q^s$ N_1, N_2 and N_3 of \mathbb{T} is an $t\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} , where $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.*

Proof. Put $Z = N_1 N_2 N_3 = \left\{ \sum_{finite} l_i m_i n_i \mid l_i \in N_1, m_i \in N_2, n_i \in N_3, i = 1, 2, \dots \right\}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} Z^3 &= (N_1 N_2 N_3)^3 \\ &= (N_1 N_2 N_3)(N_1 N_2 N_3)(N_1 N_2 N_3) \\ &\subseteq N_1(N_2 \mathbb{T} N_2 \mathbb{T} N_2)N_3 \\ &\subseteq N_1 N_2 N_3 \\ &= Z. \end{aligned}$$

Put $t = \max\{l_1, l_2, l_3, m_1, m_2, m_3, n_1, n_2, n_3\}$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z &= (N_1 N_2 N_3)\mathbb{T}^t(N_1 N_2 N_3)\mathbb{T}^t(N_1 N_2 N_3) \\
&\subseteq N_1(N_2\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}^t N_2\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}^t N_2)N_3 \\
&\subseteq N_1(N_2\mathbb{T}^{t+2}N_2\mathbb{T}^{t+2}N_2)N_3 \\
&\subseteq N_1(N_2\mathbb{T}^t N_2\mathbb{T}^t N_2)N_3 \\
&\subseteq N_1 N_2 N_3 \\
&= Z.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore Z is a $t\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Definition 3.6. (i) A TSS L of \mathbb{T} is called an l -LI if $\mathbb{T}^l L \subseteq L$.

(ii) A TSS M of \mathbb{T} is called an m -LATI if $\mathbb{T}^m M\mathbb{T}^m \subseteq M$.

(iii) A TSS N of \mathbb{T} is called an n -RI if $N\mathbb{T}^n \subseteq N$, where l, m, n are positive integers.

Theorem 3.8. Every l -LI, m -LATI and n -RI of \mathbb{T} is an $l\mathcal{B}$, $m\mathcal{B}$, $n\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} respectively.

Proof. Let L be the m -LATI of \mathbb{T} , then $\mathbb{T}^m L\mathbb{T}^m \subseteq L$. Now, $L\mathbb{T}^m L\mathbb{T}^m L \subseteq L(\mathbb{T}^m L\mathbb{T}^m)$
 $L \subseteq LLL \subseteq L$. Therefore L is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} . Similarly other cases.

Theorem 3.9. The intersection of l -LI, m -LATI and n -RI is an l -LI, m -LATI and n -RI of \mathbb{T} respectively.

Theorem 3.10. Let U_1, U_2, U_3 be an l -LI, m -LATI and n -RI of \mathbb{T} respectively. Then $U_1 \cap U_2 \cap U_3$ is an $t\mathcal{B}$, where $t = \max(l, m, n)$.

Proof. Clearly, $Z = U_1 \cap U_2 \cap U_3$ is a TSS of \mathbb{T} . By Theorem 3.8, U_1, U_2 and U_3 are $l\mathcal{B}$, $m\mathcal{B}$ and $n\mathcal{B}$ respectively. The intersection of U_1, U_2 and U_3 becomes $\max(l, m, n)$ -bi ideals by Theorem 3.5.

$$\begin{aligned}
Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z &\subseteq U_1\mathbb{T}^t U_1\mathbb{T}^t U_1 \\
&\subseteq \mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}^t U_1 \\
&= \mathbb{T}^{t+1}\mathbb{T}^{t+1}U_1 \\
&\subseteq \mathbb{T}^t U_1 \\
&\subseteq U_1.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z \subseteq U_1$.

Similarly, $Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z \subseteq U_2$ and $Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z \subseteq U_3$.

Hence $Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z \subseteq Z$.

Theorem 3.11. The product of any three tQ^s with e is a tQ^s of \mathbb{T} , where $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Theorem 3.12. Let U_1 be an $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} and U_2 be an $m\mathcal{B}$ of U_1 such that $U_2^3 = U_2$. Then U_2 is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Proof. Since U_1 is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} , $U_1\mathbb{T}^m U_1\mathbb{T}^m U_1 \subseteq U_1$ and U_2 is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of U_1 , $U_2 U_1^m U_2 U_1^m U_2 \subseteq U_2$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_2\mathbb{T}^m U_2\mathbb{T}^m U_2 &= (U_2 U_2 U_2)\mathbb{T}^m U_2\mathbb{T}^m (U_2 U_2 U_2) \\
 &= U_2 U_2 (U_2\mathbb{T}^m U_2\mathbb{T}^m U_2) U_2 U_2 \\
 &\subseteq U_2 U_2 (U_1\mathbb{T}^m U_1\mathbb{T}^m U_1) U_2 U_2 \\
 &\subseteq U_2 U_2 U_1 U_2 U_2 \\
 &= U_2 U_2 U_1 U_2 (U_2 U_2 U_2) \\
 &\subseteq U_2 (U_2 U_1 U_2 U_1 U_2) U_2 \\
 &= U_2 U_2 U_1 U_2 U_2 U_2 U_1 U_2 U_2 \\
 &= U_2 U_1^3 U_2 U_1^3 U_2 \\
 &\dots \\
 &\dots \\
 &= U_2 U_1^m U_2 U_1^m U_2 \\
 &\subseteq U_2
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, U_2 is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

Theorem 3.13. Let U_1, U_2 and U_3 be the three TSS of \mathbb{T} and $Z = U_1 U_2 U_3$. Then Z is a $t\mathcal{B}$ if at least one of U_1, U_2, U_3 is l -RI or m -LATI or n -LI of \mathbb{T} .

Proof. Let $Z = U_1 U_2 U_3$. Suppose U_1 is a l -RI of \mathbb{T} . Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z &= (U_1 U_2 U_3)\mathbb{T}^t (U_1 U_2 U_3)\mathbb{T}^t (U_1 U_2 U_3) \\
 &\subseteq U_1 (\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^t) (\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T})\mathbb{T}^t U_2 U_3 \\
 &\subseteq U_1 (\mathbb{T}^{t+2}\mathbb{T}^3\mathbb{T}^{t+1}) U_2 U_3 \\
 &\subseteq (U_1\mathbb{T}^t) U_2 U_3 \\
 &\subseteq U_1 U_2 U_3 \\
 &= Z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Suppose that U_2 is a l -RI of \mathbb{T} . Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z &= (U_1 U_2 U_3)\mathbb{T}^t (U_1 U_2 U_3)\mathbb{T}^t (U_1 U_2 U_3) \\
 &\subseteq U_1 U_2 (\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}) (\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^t) \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T} U_3 \\
 &\subseteq U_1 U_2 (\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}) \mathbb{T} U_3 \\
 &\subseteq U_1 (U_2\mathbb{T}^t) U_3 \\
 &\subseteq U_1 U_2 U_3 \\
 &= Z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Suppose that U_3 is a l -RI of \mathbb{T} . Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z\mathbb{T}^t Z\mathbb{T}^t Z &= (U_1 U_2 U_3)\mathbb{T}^t (U_1 U_2 U_3)\mathbb{T}^t (U_1 U_2 U_3) \\
 &\subseteq (U_1 U_2 U_3) (\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}) (\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}) \mathbb{T}\mathbb{T} \\
 &\subseteq (U_1 U_2 U_3) (\mathbb{T}^t\mathbb{T}\mathbb{T}^t) \mathbb{T} \\
 &\subseteq U_1 U_2 (U_3\mathbb{T}^t) \\
 &\subseteq U_1 U_2 U_3 \\
 &= Z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, Z is a $t\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} . Similar proofs for other cases.

Theorem 3.14. *Let Z be a TSS of \mathbb{T} . If U_1 is a l -RI, U_2 is a m -LATI and U_3 is a n -LI of \mathbb{T} such that $U_1U_2U_3 \subseteq Z \subseteq U_1 \cap U_2 \cap U_3$, then Z is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .*

Proof. Suppose that U_1 is a l -RI, U_2 is a m -LATI and U_3 is a n -LI of \mathbb{T} such that $U_1U_2U_3 \subseteq Z \subseteq U_1 \cap U_2 \cap U_3$. Then $Z\mathbb{T}^mZ\mathbb{T}^mZ \subseteq (U_1 \cap U_2 \cap U_3)\mathbb{T}^m(U_1 \cap U_2 \cap U_3)\mathbb{T}^m(U_1 \cap U_2 \cap U_3) \subseteq U_1(\mathbb{T}^mU_2\mathbb{T}^m)U_3 \subseteq U_1U_2U_3 \subseteq Z$. Thus, Z is a $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} .

4. VARIOUS m IDEAL GENERATORS

Theorem 4.1. *Let \mathcal{B} be a nonempty subset of \mathbb{T} . Then the $m\mathcal{B}$ generated by \mathcal{B} is $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m = \mathcal{B} \cup \sum_{finite} \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}$.*

Proof. We show that $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m = \mathcal{B} \cup \sum_{finite} \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}$ is the smallest $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} containing \mathcal{B} . Let $a, b, c \in \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m$. Then,

$$a = i_1 \text{ or } a = \sum_{finite} (s_j a_{j1} a_{j2} \dots a_{jm} t_j a_{j1} a_{j2} \dots a_{jn} r_j),$$

$$b = i_2 \text{ or } b = \sum_{finite} (s'_j a'_{j1} a'_{j2} \dots a'_{jm} t'_j a'_{j1} a'_{j2} \dots a'_{jn} r'_j) \text{ and}$$

$$c = i_3 \text{ or } c = \sum_{finite} (s''_j a''_{j1} a''_{j2} \dots a''_{jm} t''_j a''_{j1} a''_{j2} \dots a''_{jn} r''_j).$$

Where $a_{j1} a_{j2} \dots a_{jn}$, $a'_{j1} a'_{j2} \dots a'_{jn}$, $a''_{j1} a''_{j2} \dots a''_{jn}$, $a_{j1} a_{j2} \dots a_{jm}$, $a'_{j1} a'_{j2} \dots a'_{jm}$, $a''_{j1} a''_{j2} \dots a''_{jm} \in \mathbb{T}$ and $s_j, t_j, r_j, s'_j, t'_j, r'_j, s''_j, t''_j, r''_j, i_1, i_2, i_3 \in \mathcal{B}$.

Put $y = s_j a_{j1} a_{j2} \dots a_{jm} t_j a_{j1} a_{j2} \dots a_{jn} r_j$, $y' = s'_j a'_{j1} a'_{j2} \dots a'_{jm} t'_j a'_{j1} a'_{j2} \dots a'_{jn} r'_j$,
 $y'' = s''_j a''_{j1} a''_{j2} \dots a''_{jm} t''_j a''_{j1} a''_{j2} \dots a''_{jn} r''_j$.

Now, $a \cdot b \cdot c = i_1 \cdot i_2 \cdot i_3 \in \mathcal{B} \subseteq \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m$ and $a \cdot b \cdot c = \sum_{finite} y \cdot \sum_{finite} y' \cdot \sum_{finite} y'' = \sum_{finite} y \cdot y' \cdot y'' \subseteq \sum_{finite} \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B} \subseteq \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m$. Routine calculation remaining cases, $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m$

is a TSS of \mathbb{T} . Put $Q = \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}$. Now, $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m \mathbb{T}^m \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m \mathbb{T}^m \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m = \left[\mathcal{B} \cup \sum_{finite} Q \right] \mathbb{T}^m \left[\mathcal{B} \cup \sum_{finite} Q \right] \mathbb{T}^m \left[\mathcal{B} \cup \sum_{finite} Q \right] \subseteq \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}$. Thus, $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m \mathbb{T}^m \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m \mathbb{T}^m \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m \subseteq \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m$. Hence $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m$ is an m -bi ideal containing \mathcal{B} . Let Y be any other $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} containing \mathcal{B} . Then $\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B} \subseteq Y\mathbb{T}^mY\mathbb{T}^mY \subseteq Y$. Therefore $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m = \mathcal{B} \cup \sum_{finite} \mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B}\mathbb{T}^m\mathcal{B} \subseteq Y$. Hence, $\langle \mathcal{B} \rangle_m$ is the smallest $m\mathcal{B}$ of \mathbb{T} containing \mathcal{B} .

Corollary 4.2. *Let I_1 be a nonempty subset of \mathbb{T} . Then the m -LI generated by I_1 is $\langle I_1 \rangle_l = I_1 \cup \sum_{finite} \mathbb{T}^m I_1$.*

Corollary 4.3. *Let I_2 be a nonempty subset of \mathbb{T} . Then the m -RI generated by I_2 is $\langle I_2 \rangle_r = I_2 \cup \sum_{finite} I_2 \mathbb{T}^m$.*

Corollary 4.4. *Let I_3 be a nonempty subset of \mathbb{T} . Then the m -LATI generated by I_3 is $\langle I_3 \rangle_{lat} = I_3 \cup \sum_{finite} \mathbb{T}^m I_3 \mathbb{T}^m$.*

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